

METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR THE DESIGN OF CONDUCTANCE SENSORS INTENDED FOR GAS HOLDUP EVALUATION

MOUHOUB Khadidja^{*1}, AZZI Abdelwahid², HACHEMI Madjid³, BOUAM Abdallah⁴, DAHIA Ahmed⁵, MESSILEM Kamel Eddine⁶

¹Laboratory of Energy, Mechanics and Engineering, University M'hamed. Bougara, Boumerdès, 35000 Algeria

²FGMGP, LTPMP, University of Science and Technology Houari Boumediene (USTHB), Bab Ezzouar, 16111 Algeria

³Laboratory of Energy, Mechanics and Engineering, University M'hamed. Bougara, Boumerdès, 35000 Algeria

⁴Nuclear Research Centre of Birine, B.P 180, Ain Oussera 17200, Djelfa, Algeria

⁵Nuclear Research Centre of Birine, B.P 180, Ain Oussera 17200, Djelfa, Algeria

⁶Nuclear Research Centre of Birine, B.P 180, Ain Oussera 17200, Djelfa, Algeria

*Corresponding author email :kh.mouhoub@univ-boumerdes.dz

ABSTRACT: *Traditional measurement systems for gas holdup in two-phase flows exhibit significant limitations, notably the non-linearity of measured signals and a strong dependence on calibration. These constraints make their use unreliable in complex industrial environments. Yet, accurate measurement of gas holdup or gas volume fraction remains essential for understanding mass transfer, heat exchange, and fluid dynamics. The complexity of this measurement arises from the variability of flows and the diversity of fluid regimes encountered. Among the various available approaches, conductance probes offer a simple and effective solution. These probes are based on measuring the electric current passing through a two-phase mixture, thereby allowing real-time estimation of phase distribution. This article first presents a detailed review of existing techniques for measuring gas holdup, highlighting their advantages and limitations. It then introduces the design of a measurement system incorporating a conductance probe developed in the laboratory, optimized to address industrial challenges. Initial experimental results demonstrate the system's ability to accurately detect variations in gas holdup. This research offers a flexible and adaptable solution for multiphase industrial environments, ensuring more precise and reliable gas holdup measurements.*

KEYWORDS: *Gas hold-up, two-phase flows, conductance probes, local measurements.*

1 INTRODUCTION

Two-phase flows, involving multiple phases such as gas, liquid and sometimes solids occur in many industrial fields particularly in chemical engineering, oil production and nuclear engineering (Bertani, C et al., 2010; Li, H et al., 2005). One important parameter is gas holdup, representing the volumetric contribution of gas in the two-phase system. This parameter directly affects pressure drops, heat transfer and drag phenomena. In the oil sector, coaxial tube configurations are preferred to better control flow and increase hydrocarbon recovery, making the analysis of such flows essential to optimize the design and safety of industrial installations. The measurement of gas holdup relies on various techniques that differ depending on the

application. Some methods use probes that allow for direct measurement but may be affected by interaction with the fluid. Other approaches particularly ultrasonic, optical or nuclear methods offer non-intrusive measurements with enhanced accuracy, enabling reliable and rapid observation of the flows. However, these methods are often complex and expensive. In contrast, conductance probes stand out for their simplicity, low cost and ability to provide local real-time measurements, making them a promising alternative in demanding industrial environments. Understanding flow regimes and gas holdup is of major importance for characterizing the behaviour of two-phase flows. These parameters are increasingly crucial across many sectors, from chemical engineering to energy as they determine the performance and reliability of

systems. Therefore, measuring these parameters is essential to describe and understand the hydrodynamic phenomena specific to gas-liquid flows (Steven Pochet et al., 2012; Abdelkader Salim et al., 2018; IMM Babelli et al., 2002).

This article presents a comprehensive review of gas holdup measurement techniques based on electrical conductance, with a focus on the integration and design of these sensors within an electronic measurement chain. The objective is to provide a clear and concise state of the art overview that will serve as a foundation for the design and optimization of high-performance measurement systems.

2 FUNDAMENTALS OF GAS HOLDUP IN TWO-PHASE FLOWS

Gas holdup refers to the fraction of the total volume that is occupied by the gas phase in a system where both gas and liquid phases are present. It is commonly described by the gas volume fraction (GVF), which can be defined as:

$$GVF = \frac{V_g}{V_g + V_l} \quad (1)$$

Here, V_g and V_l represent the volumes of the gas and liquid phases respectively. This parameter is influenced by several factors including the velocities of each phase, operating pressure and temperature as well as the liquid's physicochemical properties. Due to the significant contrast in electrical conductivity between the gas and liquid phases, conductance-based methods offer a practical approach for estimating gas holdup. The global electrical conductance of the mixture can be modeled as a weighted average of the individual conductance often using empirical or semi-empirical relations derived from theories of heterogeneous media, such as the Maxwell-Garnett model:

$$G_{mes} = G_l \times (1 - GVF) + G_g \times GVF \quad (2)$$

- G_l is the conductance of the liquid phase.
- G_g is the conductance of the gas phase (often negligible).
- GVF represents the gas volume fraction.

In gas-liquid two-phase flows, the overall electrical conductance of the mixture results from the contributions of both phases. However, the gas phase exhibits extremely low conductivity, which is often considered negligible ($G_g \approx 0$). This assumption allows for a simplified expression of the total conductance focusing primarily on the liquid phase.

$$G_{mes} = G_l \times (1 - GVF) \quad (3)$$

3 PARAMETERS INFLUENCING GAS HOLDUP

The value of gas holdup is influenced by several parameters, including the phase velocities, pressure, temperature, and the nature of the carrying liquid. The electrical conductivity of the mixture varies significantly between the phases, which allow this difference to be used to estimate the gas holdup.

Table 1. Main factors affecting conductance measurement and associated precautions.

Factor	Main effect	Consequences / Precautions
AC signal frequency	Prevents electrode polarization	Adapt the frequency to the conductivity: high frequency for high conductivity, low frequency for low conductivity.
Temperature	Direct influence on ionic mobility	Measure and compensate for temperature variations.
Pressure	Indirect influence through density/viscosity	Less pronounced effect, to be considered in extreme conditions.
Electrode surface area (S)	Increase in surface area → Increase in measured conductance.	Calibrate according to the geometry.
Distance between electrodes (L)	Decrease in distance → Increase in conductance	Influence the cell constant.

4 INSTRUMENTAL TECHNIQUES FOR GAS HOLDUP MEASUREMENT

To date, no standard reference exists for measuring gas holdup, even though this measurement is crucial for determining the mixture density in two-phase flows, estimating pressure drop due to friction and analyzing the flow regime in pipelines. The complexity and variability of these flows make this measurement particularly challenging. This is why a significant part of our work focuses on studying the different techniques used to measure gas holdup. To ensure the efficiency and safety of systems, it is essential to adopt suitable measurement methods. Among these, conductance probes stand out as an innovative solution to quantify gas holdup. We will examine these different approaches, focusing on the use of conductance probes to design an experimental device capable of characterizing air-water two-phase flows in coaxial tubes in the laboratory.

Table 2. Summary of gas hold-up measurement methods.

Technical	Principle and Advantages
Conductance probes	<p>They measure conductivity using electrodes that pass through a mixture, with conductivity influenced by the distinct electrical properties of the liquid and gas phases, allowing the monitoring of gas hold-up. (Wang et al., 1991) highlighted the advantages of double and quadruple sensor configurations, proving their ability to provide accurate measurements even in complex mixtures. In 2012, they developed a non-contact conductivity detection sensor based on capacitive coupling (C4D), enabling the measurement of gas hold-up in stratified flows. (Wang et al., 2012)</p> <p>In 2017, their research led to more advanced techniques, enhancing the accuracy and reliability of gas hold-up measurements. (Wang, X et al., 2017)</p> <p>The work of SAIDJ and collaborators (2014, 2018) utilized conductance probes to study two-phase flows, confirming the models of Brauner and Ullmann and Nicklin et al. for predicting void fraction and velocities. (Faiza Saidj et al., 2014 ; Faiza Saidj et al., 2018 ; Brauner, N et al., 2004 ; Nicklin, D et al., 1962)</p>
Nuclear Techniques	<p>They rely on gamma ray attenuation to characterize density and gas holdup. (Kandoush et al., 1992) were among the first to demonstrate the capability of this technique to quantify gas holdup in multiphase flows. According to (Ghosh et al., 2007), this technique shows promise for real-time monitoring of liquid levels, which could support its integration into various industrial processes. (Liu et al., 2015) emphasized the importance of optimizing gamma detectors to enhance measurement accuracy. (Kumar et al., 2018) conducted a systematic comparison between this approach and other non-intrusive techniques. (Nazeim et al., 2015) developed an innovative method combining gamma attenuation with a multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network to determine gas holdup in gas-liquid flows. (Yu Zhao et al., 2016) proposed innovative approaches to enhance measurement accuracy by considering factors such as fluid temperature and the source-detector distance.</p>
Neutron tomography	<p>This imaging technique allows for accurate visualization of the internal structure of mixtures by generating detailed cross-sectional views. Its versatility has made it valuable across multiple fields: (Lerch et al., 2003) applied it effectively in the characterization of microstructures, (Kumer et al., 2010) explored its use in the investigation of phase interactions and (Brüning et al., 2015) adopted non-invasive methods based on this technique to study cultural heritage artefacts without causing damage. (Keller et al., 2017) and (Chabouh et al., 2020) enhanced detector quality and fluid mixture characterization, respectively.</p>
Ultrasonic Techniques	<p>Ultrasonic methods based on density variations detected without direct contact provide accurate measurement of gas holdup. (Addali et al., 2009 ; 2010) applied acoustic emission to analyze gas-liquid flows and characterize slug flow. (Guan et al., 2009) showed that amplitude variations could estimate gas holdup non-invasively. (Huang et al., 2011) used ultrasound to quantify bubble volumes while (Wang et al., 2013) developed a model to improve measurement accuracy. (Ofuchi et al., 2020) assessed gas holdup in swirling intermittent water–air flows by analyzing liquid film thickness and (Chaofan Li et al., 2022) proposed a technique using acoustic fluctuations while minimizing flow noise.</p>
Capacitive Techniques	<p>These rely on the dielectric permittivity to measure gas hold-up. (Geraets et al., 1987) developed a capacitive sensor capable of measuring averaged gas hold-up in a dielectric tube. (Chen et al., 2005) improved this system for industrial applications, emphasizing the importance of calibration. (E. Johana Mohamad et al., 2011) designed an Electrical Capacitance Tomography (ECT) method to image multiphase flows in pipelines based on measuring variations in dielectric permittivity inside the conduits. (Areeba Shafquet et al., 2010) experimentally tested ECT for measuring gas hold-up in bubbly two-phase flows. (Marcelo S et al., 2011) experimented with an innovative capacitive sensor aimed at quantifying gas hold-up in a natural circulation cooling circuit prototype. (Wael Ahmed et al., 2020) conducted an in-depth study on evaluating two-phase flow parameters in tube bundles. (Feng et al., 2022) integrated capacitive sensors into real-time control systems.</p>
	<p>Rely on high-speed cameras and light scattering to track bubble dynamics. (Geraets et al., 1987) were among the first to demonstrate the effectiveness of optical imaging for</p>

Non-Intrusive Optical Techniques	analyzing liquid mixtures. (E. Johana Mohamad et al., 2011) explored the use of these techniques to monitor gas holdup in real time in complex flows. (Wang et al., 2012) used high-speed camera imaging to examine bubble dynamics and obtain precise measurements of their size and distribution. (Sharma et al., 2012) studied the influence of optical probes on bubble dynamics, highlighting their capability to measure gas holdup. (Zhao et al., 2016) developed light scattering-based techniques to characterize bubbles, allowing direct estimation of gas holdup. (Huajun Li et al., 2016) introduced optical tomography approaches to visualize the internal structure of fluid mixtures.
Venturi Tubes (Differential Pressure)	They establish a relationship between differential pressure and gas retention through empirical correlations. (Chisholm et al., 1973) were among the pioneers in this field, proposing empirical correlations linking pressure drop to gas-liquid phase parameters. (Zeghloul et al., 2021) demonstrated that a Venturi with a diameter ratio of 0.55 provides the best correlations for various flow regimes using differential pressure sensors and conductance probes. (Messilem et al., 2020) developed a new correlation improving mass flow rate measurement and confirmed the importance of Venturi geometry. These studies show that Venturi tubes combined with conductance probes constitute a reliable method for industrial measurements of gas retention.
Artificial Intelligence (AI)	The use of Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) for measuring gas hold-up has seen promising development. This innovative method allows modeling the complex interactions between flow conditions and gas hold-up. (Aryan Veisi et al., 2023) developed an ANN model validated with COMSOL to predict gas hold-up in oil pipelines, while (Ramy Mohammed et al., 2023) combined an eight-electrode capacitive sensor with a multilayer perceptron (MLP) neural network for more reliable industrial measurements.

5 DISCOVERING CONDUCTANCE PROBES: PRINCIPLES AND CHALLENGES

The principle of conductance probes is based on evaluating the electrical conductivity of the fluid using two immersed electrodes. This conductivity varies significantly between the liquid and gas phases, making these probes suitable for evaluating gas holdup. Jones and Zuber. (1975) demonstrated that the electrode configuration and sampling frequency play a crucial role in improving the temporal and spatial resolution of measurements. In such situations, classical signal processing techniques are insufficient to guarantee measurement accuracy (Jones, O.C et al., 1975). Conductance probes have the advantage of being non-intrusive provided they are carefully designed not to disturb the flow. This aspect is particularly important in annular flow regimes where the liquid film is very thin: a poorly integrated probe could distort measurements by perturbing the wave dynamics at the film surface. To adapt to various industrial applications, self-adaptive probes have been developed, such as the ring-electrode probe by (M. Fossa et al., 1998) (Tsochatzidis et al., 1992) where two ring-shaped electrodes surround the pipe wall oriented perpendicular to the flow.

(Azzopardi, B. J. 2006) highlighted major advancements in phase distribution measurement through the development of multi-electrode probes.

These devices enhance spatial resolution and enable more precise analysis of gas-liquid flow dynamics along the pipeline. (Lina, Y et al., 2009) used a configuration with four ring electrodes to assess the water fraction in an oil-water flow, where oil flowed through the center and water formed a peripheral layer. These probes also offer better accuracy for characterizing phase variations in dynamic flows. (Coney et al., 1973) developed a probe with two rectangular electrodes to measure the thickness of wavy films while minimizing flow disturbances. Another variant, the three-electrode probe, uses one transmitting electrode and two segmented receiving electrodes to measure the current ratio, thus allowing compensation for temperature effects on conductivity. (Kyu Byung Lee et al., 2017) implemented this design to determine liquid film thickness under variable temperature conditions, proving that the current ratio remains stable despite conductivity changes due to temperature — a crucial factor for accurately assessing gas holdup in unstable environments. (M. Fossa et al., 1998) also explored the use of two plate electrodes 3 mm in diameter spaced 9 mm apart along the pipe axis for precise conductance measurements. Meanwhile, (M. S. Ko et al., 2015) and (Yeon-Gun Lee et al., 2017) developed advanced conductance sensors to improve gas holdup measurement. Generally, conductance probes use a high-frequency AC/DC current to avoid ionic polarization phenomena and unwanted electrochemical reactions. Finally, (Ghendour.N et al., 2021) focused their research on optimizing gas

holdup measurement in annular flows. They designed a 2.2RE multi-electrode probe capable of measuring gas holdup by detecting conductivity variations between strategically placed ring electrodes. Thanks to optimized design and numerical simulations, this probe offers high precision and sensitivity with a linear relationship between output voltage and gas volume fraction (GVF). Experiments showed low relative error compared to numerical predictions, thus validating the effectiveness of this method for precise measurements in complex two-phase flows.

Fig.1 Proposed probe 2.2RE: (a) schematic of the electrodes configuration and measurement strategy, (b) installation of the probe in the annulus channel. (Ghendour.N et al., 2021)

(Kramer et al., 2024) introduced a new generation of dual-tip conductivity probes for self-aerated air–water flows. Featuring printed circuit board electrodes and a detachable sensor head the design enhances measurement precision, durability and ease of replacement compared to traditional needle-type probes. This advancement aims to improve the repeatability of experiments and broaden access to air–water flow research.

To address the challenges of measuring complex and heterogeneous gas–liquid flows, (Chenjun Hu et al., 2025) proposed an innovative approach based on multi-sensor data fusion. By combining liquid volume fraction measurements from Electrical Resistance Tomography (ERT) and Electrical Capacitance Tomography (ECT) with total flow rate data from a Venturi meter, they were able to separately estimate gas and liquid flow rates. This method enables accurate assessment of gas holdup across a wide range of conditions, maintaining a relative error below 10% even under complex flow regimes.

Conductance probes used to measure gas holdup automatically adjust their parameters (such as sampling frequency, electrode configuration, or conductivity detection thresholds) to adapt to conductivity variations caused by the fluctuating presence of gas. This adaptive capability allows them to maintain high measurement accuracy even when gas holdup changes rapidly, thereby ensuring reliable and dynamic readings even in unstable environments. These probes are ideally suited for integration into industrial installations, providing real-time monitoring of gas holdup in various processes such as extraction, filtration or multiphase flows.

6 OPERATING PRINCIPLE OF CONDUCTANCE PROBES ACCORDING TO THE FLOW REGIME

Fig. 2 Schemas of updating phases through the concentric ring. (EF Caetano et al., 1992)

Table 3. Conductance probe response according to two-phase flow regimes. (EF Caetano et al., 1992)

Flow regime	Description	Signal characteristic	Use and Adaptation
Bubbly flow regime	Small gas bubbles dispersed in a continuous liquid phase.	Brief low-conductance spikes when a bubble passes. Irregular, granular signal proportional to the gas volume fraction.	Well suited for local measurement of gas hold-up. Used in bubble columns and vertical flows with low gas flow rates. Typical signal: a series of short dips.
Annular flow regime	Gas flows in the center surrounded by an annular liquid film.	Nearly constant and low signal. Electrodes are rarely fully immersed in the liquid.	Less suitable for conventional probes. Difficult interpretation often requires complementary techniques typical signal: low noise, without sharp transitions.
Slug flow regime	Alternating long liquid slugs and elongated gas bubbles.	Sharp transitions between high conductivity (liquid) and zero conductivity (gas).	Precise measurement of the residence times of each phase reliable estimation of gas hold-up. Very well suited for conductance probes. Typical signal: clear alternation of high and low plateaus.

7 DESIGN METHODOLOGIES: APPROACHES AND CHALLENGES

7.1 Experimental Methodology

Table 4. Evolution of conductance probe configurations for gas Hold-up analysis in two-phase flows

	Methodology	Experimental Results
2.0RE	An initial experimental configuration (2.0RE) based on two annular electrodes was deployed in a pipe to test the conductivity method. This setup enabled both local and global measurements of gas hold-up in a gas-liquid flow, thereby validating the feasibility of the technique. (E.N. Eyo et al., 2019)	<p>The diagram illustrates the Probe 2.0RE configuration. Part (a) is a cross-sectional view showing two annular electrodes: an 'Excitation Electrode' (red) and a 'Ground' electrode (blue). Dimensions shown include OD (Outer Diameter), ID (Inner Diameter), and electrode thickness. Part (b) is a perspective view of the probe inserted into a pipe, showing the 'Flow' direction and the 'Ring Electrodes'.</p>

1RE.CT	To refine the results, four pairs of electrodes were installed along an annular channel composed of two concentric tubes. This multipoint approach (1RE.CT) enables the measurement of the axial profile of gas hold-up and the observation of local variations depending on the geometry and flow regime. It proves particularly relevant for characterizing complex flows in industrial applications. (X. Sun et al., 2004)	
2.2RE	The (2.2RE) probe relies on the use of two symmetrical excitation electrodes with a shared potential and grounded reference electrodes. This configuration provides a more refined measurement of gas hold-up in two-phase flows, particularly in annular flows, by offering improved resolution of phase distribution. (Ghendour.N et al., 2021)	

7.2 Modeling and Optimization of Conductance Probes

Modeling conductance probes in two-phase flows requires an in-depth study of several key parameters, notably the geometry of the coaxial tube, the distribution of phases (gas and liquid) and the electrical properties of the fluids (conductivity and permittivity). These factors directly influence the accuracy, sensitivity and robustness of the measurements. Probes are therefore designed to meet the specific requirements of two-phase flows by using advanced numerical simulation techniques to optimize their configuration as well as their spatial and temporal resolution. To enhance the sensitivity of the probes and their adaptability to complex flows, various numerical approaches such as the Finite Element Method (FEM) and Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) are employed. These methods allow modeling the interaction between the probes and the fluids and determining the most appropriate configuration while minimizing errors caused by interference (Ghendour.N et al., 2021).

Early work by (Tsochatzidis et al., 2002) demonstrated the importance of multi-electrode probes and their arrangement to capture local

variations in gas holdup, with applications in the petroleum, chemical and nuclear industries.

Furthermore, (Zhao et al., 2021) enriched numerical models by integrating more complex fluid properties.

(Xiaoxiao Dong et al., 2017) developed an advanced methodology for analyzing signals from conductance probes, enabling a notable improvement in measurement accuracy and resolution under complex flow regimes. The unstable and dynamic flow regimes encountered in real industrial installations can compromise measurement accuracy. These probes are also subject to non-linearity and require careful calibration to maintain their reliability. Moreover, integrating these probes within complex measurement systems coupled with advanced filtering and modeling techniques remains an ongoing research area to enhance their robustness and applicability in extreme environments. (Abubakar et al., 2021) explored conductance measurement technologies in multiphase environments, highlighting their applicability and the challenges encountered under varied conditions.

8 PROPOSED DESIGN OF THE CONDUCTANCE SENSOR

The sensor design is based on a coaxial four-electrode configuration that allows for the

measurement of the electrical conductivity of water to estimate gas hold-up in air–water flows. To improve spatial resolution, several electrode modules are distributed longitudinally along the pipeline. Each module is connected to a dedicated electronic circuit optimized to ensure reliable signal acquisition while minimizing electromagnetic interference and precision losses due to ambient noise. Signal processing is carried out in real time by an integrated microcontroller that calculates the volumetric fractions of gas from the conductance measurements. For advanced analysis and graphical representation of the collected data a software environment such as MATLAB is used. This platform enables the application of adaptive filtering techniques, the detection of rapid flow fluctuations and the generation of dynamic visualizations of phase distribution. A prototype is envisioned as a chain of ten identical sensors interconnected via an industrial programmable logic controller (PLC) enabling simultaneous measurements across multiple sections of the pipeline. The current setup is implemented on a coaxial pipe with an external diameter of 60 mm and an internal diameter of 40 mm. This modular architecture offers high flexibility for adapting to various flow configurations and allows easy system expansion to meet the specific requirements of each industrial application. It thus represents a significant advancement in the study and characterization of complex multiphase flows.

Fig. 3 Representation of the conductance sensor simulation in LTspice.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4 (a): Test of the developed conductance sensor, (b): 3D view of the electrical circuit of the conductance sensor.

9 CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

This study highlighted the potential of conductance probes for measuring gas holdup in two-phase flows. When combined with appropriate electronic circuits, this approach offers promising prospects for improving measurement accuracy and device robustness while ensuring better adaptability to varying flow conditions. At this end, a conductance sensor was designed and fabricated. Current research efforts focus on developing the complete measurement chain that will fully leverage the capabilities of this sensor. This measurement chain will be centralized by a programmable logic controller (PLC) to continuously collect and process all parameters related to two-phase flows. In the short term, the work will aim to validate the reliability and accuracy of the obtained measurements and to characterize the flow regimes. In the longer term, the objective is to develop a robust and adaptable system providing real-time data for the control and optimization of industrial processes.

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